

NEOVASCULOSTOP

PARADIGM SHIFT IN NEOVASCULARIZATION TREATMENT

NeoVasculoStop

EIC funded Pathfinder project that plans to bring a paradigm shift in retinopathy's therapeutic treatment.

Contact us

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Partners

- Experimentica
- Experimentica UAB
- Vichem Chemie
- Semmelweis University
- Emmes Biopharma
- Laser Consult

Retinopathies

are expected to increase with an aging population and the increased prevalence of diabetes.

Our vision

We believe that orally bioavailable medications would revolutionize the treatment of retinopathies, by reducing adverse effects, sustaining vision, lowering the direct and indirect financial burden associated with these diseases, and increasing access to healthcare.

Our novel strategy of drug targeting will not only enrich the modified molecules in retinal tissue but will also reduce the therapeutic oral dose compared to existing anti-angiogenic therapy in cancer thereby increasing the safety of the treatment.

Our final objectives

Orally available

Non-invasive

Easy to use

Reduces costs

Reduces non-compliance

Improves eyesight

Current treatment

injections to the eye require outpatient visits and can be associated with adverse effect.

European
Innovation
Council

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